

POSSIBILITIES OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION MEANS IN THE FORMATION OF VOLITIONAL QUALITIES IN SCHOOLCHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the essence and structure of physical education means used in the author's dissertation research, the possibilities of these means, their manifestation in adolescence and the peculiarities of their formation. The methods of using a complex program in the formation of volitional qualities, the importance of exercises in the formation of volitional qualities, as well as the methods used in the formation of such qualities in schoolchildren as overcoming various difficulties in the learning process are analyzed.

Key words: volitional qualities, possibilities of physical education, formation of volitional qualities, means of physical education.

Throughout the history of the development of philosophical, psychological and pedagogical knowledge, from ancient times to the present day, the problem of the concept of "will" has always attracted the attention of scientists. None of the scientific directions has denied the existence of this phenomenon in humans. Regardless of who wrote it and when, almost all textbooks in psychology and pedagogy have shed light on this problem in one way or another. Let us now turn to the basic philosophical, psychological, and pedagogical definitions of the concept of will and its manifestation. In the history of European philosophy, it had two main meanings. According to classical rationalist traditions, the will is the ability of the mind to self-determine, including the creation of moral and

specific causality. F.V.Shelling, Shopengauer, E. Hartmann, F .; Nietzsche and partly A. According to the voluntaristic tradition introduced by Bergson, the will is a fundamental property of pre-cognitive being and is the basis of all explanatory models. In psychology, the concept of "will" is presented as a complex mental process that makes a person active and motivates him to act in accordance with the purpose and achieve the set goals. Unlike other psychological phenomena, the will is not measured by specific measurements and evaluations, but this does not rule out the possibility of studying the human will scientifically, especially experimentally [1]. Let's talk about all of them because they are of interest in the context of our research. 1. Will is a certain internal force of a psychological trait capable of controlling other psychological phenomena and human behavior. 2. Will is a form of internal control of actions performed by a person and associated with his consciousness, thinking, acceptance. 3. Willpower is the highest level of regulation of human behavior. Volitional behavior is called volitional because a person can control it. 4. Willpower is the ability of a person to set and achieve difficult goals, to overcome serious internal and external obstacles. 5. Willpower is when a person consciously chooses one of the types of behaviors that exist on an equal level and chooses to follow one of them. 6. Willpower is a feature that distinguishes human behavior from animal behavior. Animals have no will, they act under the influence of external environmental factors or factors of internal organic properties. 7. The will is the source of human conscious and perceptual actions.

As you can see, in understanding the concept of "will" it is impossible to distinguish only the psychological or pedagogical aspect, because it affects all areas related to human activity. E.P. Ilin, L.S. Vygotskiy, I.D. In their pedagogical research, scholars such as Bex analyzed various aspects of the formation (development) of different categories of willpower among students, military cadets, sports school students, which led us to draw the following

conclusions: 1. There is a clear pedagogical concept of willpower and willpower not; 2. In pedagogy, the problem of will and volitional qualities is considered not by their essence, but by formation, development, so the subject of research is studied not the essence of events, but their forms, methods of their development, formation. 3. The basis for the development (design) of various systems, models, programs, technologies is selected by the authors on the basis of the goals and objectives of the study, one of the existing psychological concepts of will and volitional qualities. Our understanding of the nature and content of volitional qualities in students is based on the following theoretical principles: - volitional qualities are a relatively independent, stable mental formation of man, the content of which is determined by the stage of ontogeny, personal experience, knowledge, skills, formed motives and views; - volitional qualities act as a unified, open, dynamic, integrated system, the components of which are interconnected, depending on the objective conditions of a particular activity, and ensure the superiority of this or that volitional quality; - The system-forming function of volitional qualities is the generalized ability to overcome various difficulties that arise in the way of achieving a goal; - The success of the activity and the degree of formation of volitional qualities are interrelated: the formation of volitional qualities is determined by the nature and content of the activity, in turn, the success of the activity depends on the level of formation of volitional qualities [2, 3, 4]. In pedagogy, the term tools has an ambiguous content and is used by researchers in different senses. These are teaching aids, educational tools, development tools, humanitarian culture tools, and more. In addition, tools are a necessary and important element of the educational process and can also be considered as a means of increasing (improving) the effectiveness of any teaching, learning, upbringing process through certain forms and methods of teaching and education. Therefore, the most common and generally accepted definition of tools in pedagogy is as follows: pedagogical tools are material (man-

made) and natural objects used in the learning process as a carrier of information in the learning process, a tool for organizing and managing students' learning activities [5]. With this general definition, any object used in the educational process can be considered a "tool". There is a certain difference between researchers in the typology of tools. Most often in pedagogy there are the following types of teaching aids: printed, electronic, audiovisual, visual, demonstration, presentation, educational devices, simulators and sports equipment, teaching aids, which in turn are divided into different types. The article focuses on the equipment of sports equipment and gyms, sports grounds, school stadiums as the main means of education. And in this sense, they can be considered as means of solving specific problems of physical education, training and upbringing. Indeed, gymnastic ladders, beams, balls, etc., do not in themselves develop any volitional quality, they are merely “material means” used in physical education to solve certain pedagogical problems. Therefore, in order to determine the structure and capabilities of physical education tools used to develop the volitional qualities of students, the author considered it necessary to refer to the theory and methodology of physical education as a separate pedagogical discipline. The theory and methodology of physical education emphasizes that its means include exercise, the healing forces of nature and the rules and norms of hygiene [6]. Let us now describe each group of physical education tools based on these sources. Exercise. Most authors consider them to belong to the basic means of physical education. Exercise is a set of movements that are formed and organized according to its laws, aimed at the implementation of the tasks of physical education. The term "physical" in this sense reflects the essence of the work manifested in the form of the movements of the human body and its parts in space and time. The term "exercise" refers to the focused repetition of actions in order to affect a person's physical and mental characteristics and to improve the way they perform that action. That is, exercise

is seen on the one hand as a specific motor movement, on the other hand, as a process of repeating it many times. The effectiveness of exercise depends primarily on their content. According to the definition of sports physiologists, the content of exercise is a combination of physiological, psychological and biomechanical processes that occur in the human body during this exercise. The content of exercise determines their health-promoting importance, educational role, and impact on the development of personality traits that are particularly important to us. The effect of exercise on the development of personality traits is that in the process of exercise overcomes various difficulties and manages emotional feelings, develops vital qualities, including volitional qualities. Most of the physical activity in school is done with a group of peers. In addition, in many cases, the actions of one student determine the actions of others, which is especially evident in sports competitions and outdoor games. The ability to exercise self-control, to submit to the will of the team, to find one right decision, and to help a friend regardless of personal ambitions are volitional qualities that are actively formed through exercise. The healing powers of nature have a significant effect on those who exercise. Changes in meteorological conditions can contribute to the activation of physical activity, create additional difficulties in the performance of exercise and, as a result, increase the effectiveness of the development of volitional qualities. In the process of physical education of students, the healing forces of nature, as a rule, are used in two directions: 1) as factors that create the most favorable conditions for exercise. At the same time, exercise increases its impact on schoolchildren. In the forest, lessons on the shores of the watershed help to activate biological processes, increase overall performance, slow down the fatigue process, and more. 2) as a relatively independent means of healing and strengthening the body of a growing adolescent, which is also important for the development of their volitional qualities. At the same time, in the context of the development of volitional

qualities, the most important direction is their systematic and integrated application in conjunction with exercise. Hygienic rules and norms can be applied as a means of physical education in the development of volitional qualities in both directions. First, as an independent tool. For students, following a daily routine, reading, eating routine is not such a simple task and requires little willpower from them. Constant motivation to follow routines greatly contributes to their development. Second, it is used as a condition that helps to promote health and increase the effectiveness of the effects of exercise [7]. Thus, the means of physical education for the formation of the volitional qualities of students include exercise, the healing forces of nature, the rules and norms of hygiene. They are closely related to each other, complementing and conditioning the effectiveness of the application. During adolescence, educational activities and the situation between those around you change significantly. Learning (like all other types of activities) is more complex, requiring more effort, independence, and greater responsibility. Adults' attitudes toward students also change: they expect mature, adult behaviors, including the display of volitional and personal traits, from adolescence. This is of course natural. Because the teenager will be smarter, stronger, physically developed. His place in the community of his peers, and public opinion about him, begins to be of great importance to the teenager. In this case, because the requirements of adults and peers are different and different from each other, each time he will have to make a choice that requires high willpower [8]. All this has a direct effect on the manifestation of volitional qualities, which determine their developmental characteristics at this age. The author studied and analyzed a number of studies on the development of volitional qualities in students, came to the following conclusions describing their manifestation and developmental characteristics: - The process of voluntary development of students is closely linked with moral education. involves the formation of motives. - Willpower qualities in students

are manifested in the unity of opposite positive and negative aspects: courage and fear, desire and opportunity, tenacity and weakness, endurance and inability to behave, and so on. - Students prioritize the development of volitional qualities by choosing from all possible personal qualities. People with strong wills are the ideal person for most students, students want to be like them, to imitate them [9]. According to many researchers, the level of development of volitional qualities in students does not meet the requirements of the changing social environment for them. Adolescent students are not well organized, easily succumb to difficulties, are easily influenced by others, and often behave against previously learned demands and rules of behavior. Of course, the formation and development of willpower qualities in students does not go backwards and their level does not decrease compared to younger school students. Many adolescent students are unprepared for such conditions simply because they live in more complex social conditions that require them to have higher forms of self-regulation, including more active expression of willpower qualities. At the same time, in this process, students develop the ability to analyze their own behavior, their own personal attitude to the environment, role models, demands on themselves. Moreover, these requirements often do not correspond to the ability to meet them. As a result, adolescent students often feel like people with weak wills, which leads them to feel dissatisfied, to feel dissatisfied. Thus, adolescence is a special period in human life. It is the age of not only the pursuit of knowledge, the energy of indifference, violent activity, thirst for activity, but also the active development of all personal qualities, including volitional qualities. Therefore, it is very important to activate such factors during this period, which encourage adolescents to the constant manifestation of volitional qualities, develop them and add them to the list of necessary personal qualities. Therefore, the means of physical education have a special place among them [10]. The analysis of the composition of the means of physical education and their interrelation with the peculiarities of

the development and manifestation of volitional qualities in students allowed to determine their following possibilities. First. Physical education tools allow students to satisfy their desire for physical improvement, accelerate their development, strengthen their health, and meet their need for harmonious development. Secondly. They instill in students the desire to be imitated, as well as to be people who have achieved certain success in sports, are physically fit, have high personal qualities and prestige. Third. They instill in students a natural desire to win in competition with others, to stand out from others, to assert themselves, to gain prestige, to be first, to increase self-interest, to take a worthy place in peer circle, to be recognized and respected. Fourth. They develop a variety of movement skills and abilities, allow them to test themselves in overcoming difficulties, nurture behavior. Fifth. It satisfies the needs of teenagers for dynamic movement, novelty, different emotions, communication with peers. Sixth. They form a motivational motivation through the need for students to participate in physical education classes even if they do not want to meet the requirements of the curriculum. It was noted that the identified opportunities of physical education tools in the development of the volitional qualities of students affect them to varying degrees. These opportunities are realized not by themselves, but through an integrated pedagogical process, such as physical education classes, school physical education activities, sports competitions, classes in sports clubs, and so on. The progress of the work done and the analysis of their results allowed to draw the following general conclusions. Conclusion. Equipping the school with sports facilities and equipment is not crucial for the organization of work on the formation of volitional qualities. While this is very important for optimizing work on the development of physical qualities, it is not a very important factor in the formation of a strong will in students. The reader can be strong and agile, and at the same time be courageous, enterprising, and unable to make independent

decisions. Our observations on the implementation of the volitional qualities formation program show that exercise should be sufficiently difficult for the formation and development of volitional qualities in students. And at the same time, they need to be tailored to each student individually, otherwise he loses interest in implementing them if he realizes he can't master them. This is confirmed by the general results of the previously presented study. Thus, the planned and systematic work on the use of physical education opportunities in the formation of volitional qualities in students has yielded positive results. This goal-orientation was reflected in a significant increase in the number of students with a high level of initiative.

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